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Perceived effects of Alcohol intake among Students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

JAMES, Bariaara Promise*

Tel+1237039249650 Email address: jamesbariaarapromise(at)gmail(dot)com

Department of Health and Safety Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Dr. WABAH Goodnews**

TEL +2347063842842 Department of Sociology Ignatius, Ajuru University of Education.

Dr. ONYIRI, Chinenyenwa Jacqueline

Department of Health and Safety Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Dr. Aduadua Bennett OFFOR***

Tel+2348064310030 Email address: adusbennett11(at)gmail(dot)com

Department of Health and Safety Study, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Corresponding author: Dr. G. Wabah

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the perceived effects of alcohol intake among Students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. Four null hypotheses were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive cross sectional survey was adopted for the study with 10,856 undergraduates as the study population. The sample size of 386 was calculated using Cochran formula which was selected using two- stage sampling procedures. The Reliability coefficient value of 0.80 for the validated instrument was obtained using Pearson Products Moment Correlation Coefficient. The data collected was analyzed using Statistical Products for Service Solution (SPSS) version 25.0) using regression analysis was adopted to test the null hypotheses. The result in table 1.1 above revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived health effect among students [$f(4,390) = 10.953, p < 0.05$]. The result in table 1.2 above revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived physical effect among students [$f(4,390) = 8.798, p < 0.05$]. The result in table 4.9 above revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived social effect among students [$f(4,390) = 14.147, p < 0.05$]. The result in table 4.10 above revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived mental effect among students [$f(4,390) = 14.147, p < 0.05$]. Conclusively, it was observed from the findings that heavy alcohol intake exposes the undergraduates of IAUE to several health problems such as physical, social, psychological effects. Among others, it was recommended that University management should establish a monitoring team to police the nooks and crannies of the environment where illicit substances are taken.

Keywords

Health effect, Alcohol intake, Students.

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Introduction

On universities campuses across Nigeria, alcohol related culture is entwined in school customs, social norms, and the academic institution itself. Although the majority of college undergraduates are below the legal drinking age, alcohol continues to be widely used on most institutions today. The effects of heavy or “binge” drinking pose serious risk for drinkers, but also for those in the immediate environment (Wechsler *et al.*, 2014). Heavy drinking has been associated with physical or sexual assault, criminal violations, and unsafe sexual activity. Heavy alcohol use has also been linked to adverse health effects including vehicle accidents, injuries, and accidental deaths. In research on tertiary institutions students, heavy drinkers have been found to have lower academic grades, miss class, and to fall behind in school work most often. The National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism (NIAAA) (2014) reported that 4 of 5 university students drink alcohol. Hence, half of all university students who consume alcohol drink heavily. Alcohol is a psychoactive drug that has a depressant effect. People have been brewing and fermenting alcoholic drinks since the dawn of civilization. Consumed moderate amount, alcoholic beverages are relaxing and in some cases may even have beneficial effects in heart, health, consumed in excess alcohol is poisonous to human systems and is considered a drug (Krieger, *et al.*, 2018). Studies of Samuel and James (2018) reported that good proportion of students in tertiary education institution had use at least one form of illicit drugs and are likely to contribute to different physical and psychological dependence.

When people take (think) alcohol, it is absorbed into their bloodstream. It affects the central nervous system (the brain and spinal cord), which controls virtually all body functions. The immediate physical effects of drinking alcohol range from mild mood changes to complete loss of coordination, vision, balance and speech, any which can be signals of acute alcohol intoxication or drunkenness. These effects usually wear-off in a matter of hours after a person stops drinking (Marshall *et al.*, 2011). The word ‘alcohol’ probably has its origin in Arabic meaning ‘a fine dust’ or ‘essence’. There are four main types of alcohol: Methyl Alcohol- CH_3OH , Ethyl Alcohol- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, Propyl Alcohol- $\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$ and Butyl Alcohol- $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$. Ethyl Alcohol is the one of the intoxicating drinks, and its concentration ranges from 4 to 59%. Alcohol has very valuable antiseptic properties, and when used outside the body is very useful chemical (A guide to Family Health, 1983 as cited in Awoyinfa, 2012).

Onongha (2012) stated that an alcohol beverage is a drink containing ethanol commonly known as alcohol. Alcoholic beverages are divided into three general classes: Beers, Wines and Spirits. They are legally consumed in most countries, and over one hundred countries have laws regulating their production, sale and consumption. In particular, such laws specify the minimum age at which a person may legally buy or drink them. This minimum age varies between sixteen and twenty-five years, depending upon the country and the type of drink. Most nations set it at eighteen years of age. The production and consumption of alcohol occurs in most cultures of the world, from hunter-gatherer peoples to nation-states (Koehler, 2013). Alcoholic beverages are often an important part of social events in these cultures.

According to World Health Organization (WHO) (2019), in many parts of the world, drinking alcoholic beverages is a common feature of social gatherings. Nevertheless, the consumption of alcohol carries a risk of adverse health and social consequences related to its intoxicating, toxic and dependence, producing properties. In addition to the chronic diseases that may develop in those who drink large amounts of alcohol over a number of years, alcohol U.K. is also associated with an increased risk of acute health conditions such as injuries, including from traffic accidents. There is a general belief that alcohol performs a number of services that have become almost indispensable to

modern society and living. In as much as alcohol is a reliable means for social integration, as well as symbol of social solidarity and also lubricant for social intercourse during which it provides the much needed atmosphere for the exchange of ideas, information and discussion of politics, the ills or detriment of excessive alcohol intake cannot be ignored or overlooked (Popovska, 2012).

Several event that take place on the campus are more likely to promote alcohol which has a perceived health effects and most recently for protection against coronary heart disease. There is evidence of cardiovascular benefits from drinking one to two drinks per day; however, the health benefits from moderate intake of alcohol are controversial. Alcohol should be regarded as a recreational drug with potentially serious adverse effects on health and it is not recommended for cardio-protection in the place of safer and proven traditional methods such as exercise and proper nutrition (Pedersen et al. 2010). Larger amounts of blood alcohol can impair brain function and eventually cause unconsciousness. An extreme overdose of alcohol poisoning can be fatal. Alcohol taken in excess can depress brain activities to the point where memory muscular coordination and balance can be disturbed hence the reason for concern as regards this situation amongst students with emphasis on Universities especially in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.

Purposeful production of alcoholic beverages is common in many cultures and often reflects their cultural and religious peculiarities as much as their geographical and sociological conditions. Alcohol is used by certain persons for several reasons, based on several factors. Its use is related to factors ranging from emotional, social, religious, physical, to psychological. Some of the reasons why people take alcohol therefore includes: to quench thirst, to promote sleep, to spice up social gathering, to improve appetite, to kill anxiety, influence from other people and to relieve pains. Heavy alcohol use affects many parts of the brain, but the most vulnerable cells are those associated with memory, coordination, and judgment. Dangerous drinking is likely to affect students disproportionately. The health consequences a student may experience as a result of dangerous drinking have an expected range, from manageable situations to potentially fatal outcomes. Alcohol abuse has physiological and psychological effects on students, as it inhibits students' performance in a way that their cognitive abilities are affected by even small amounts of alcohol and can persist for a substantial period of time after the acute effects of alcohol impairment disappear. Becerra and Becerra. (2020) reported on the prevalence of psychosocial and mental effect of heavy alcohol intake and other substances which affect the health status of the undergraduates such as drop-out, low academic grade .For example, alcohol may impair memory by slowing down the transfer and coordination of information and may reduce students' ability to remember information that was learned prior to going out for drinks. Chow et al. (2021) affirmed that the prevalence of anxiety, depression and psychological distress are high among undergraduates. This studies report a wide array or variety of consequences associated with the alcohol. For instance, in Ignatius University of Education, when male students who are drunk during matriculation ceremony, students will be driving cars with the influence of alcohol, some to the extent of hitting fence with their car(s), even shooting, spreading of money uncontrollable and also misbehaving and harassing girl while among female students, consumption of heavy alcohol may increase their risk of being victims of date rape, unwanted sex, harassment and physical assault which can lead to unwanted pregnancy and also abortion. It is interesting to know that excessive intake of alcohol is detrimental to the health and wellbeing of an individual, and students who are supposed to be enlightened still indulge in drinking alcohol excessively especially among Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. This brings to mind the need to know why this is so. Poised to this background, the researcher seek to investigate the perceived effects of alcohol intake among Students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate the perceived effects of alcohol intake among undergraduate students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived health effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State
2. There is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived physical effect of alcohol intake among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State
3. There is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived social effect of alcohol intake among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State
4. There is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived mental effect of alcohol intake among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

Methodology

Area of the Study: The area of this study was Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni Port Harcourt, Rivers State which was the defunct Rivers State College of Education. This institution has three campuses with a central campus located in Rumuolumeni of Obio/Akpor local Government Area of Rivers State and others located in Ndele and St John respectively

The research design is a descriptive cross-sectional study. The population of the study consisted of 10,856 students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt (Academic Planning Office, 2022).

The sample size of 386 was calculated using Cochran formula. The study assumes 95 percent level of confidence. Based on these assumptions, the required sample size will be calculated as under:

$$\frac{n = Z^2 Pq}{e^2}$$

n= sample size

Z = critical value of confidence Limit = 1.96

e= error margin = 0.05

p= Estimated proportion of an attribute present in the population = 0.50

q = 1-p = 0.50

A two stage sampling procedure was adopted to select the sample for this study.

Stage 1: Simple random sampling techniques was used to select the main campus of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt of the 3 campuses of the institution. Stage 2: A simple random sampling technique was also used to students both male and female in various levels and department to achieve the desired sample size. The instrument for eliciting information for this study was structured questionnaire titled Questionnaire on perceived effect of drug abuse. The instrument was in five sections A, B, C, D, and E. The Reliability coefficient value of 0.80 was

obtained using Pearson Products Moment Correlation Coefficient. Hence the instrument was reliable and adopted for the study. The data collected were coded and analyzed using Statistical Products for Service Solution (SPSS) version 25.0) using regression analysis was adopted to test the null hypotheses.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived health effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Table 1.1: Regression analysis on significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived health effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	9.686	4	2.422	10.953	.000	Rejected
	Residual	86.222	390	.221			
	Total	95.909	394				

***Significant, $p < 0.05$**

The result in table 1.1 above revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived health effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [$f(4,390) = 10.953, p < 0.05$]. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived health effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived physical effect of alcohol intake among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Table 1.2: Regression analysis on significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived physical effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	35.190	4	8.798	56.507	.000	Rejected
	Residual	60.719	390	.156			
	Total	95.909	394				

***Significant, $p < 0.05$**

The result in table 1.2 above revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived physical effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [$f(4,390) = 8.798, p < 0.05$]. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived physical effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State was rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived social effect of alcohol intake among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Table 1.3: Regression analysis on significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived social effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	12.152	4	3.038	14.147	.000	Rejected
	Residual	83.756	390	.215			
	Total	95.909	394				

***Significant, $p < 0.05$**

The result in table 4.9 above revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived social effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [$f(4,390) = 14.147, p < 0.05$]. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived social effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State was rejected.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived mental effect of alcohol intake among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Table 1.4: Regression analysis on significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived mental effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
1	Regression	31.443	3	10.481	63.571	.000	Rejected
	Residual	64.465	391	.165			
	Total	95.909	394				

***Significant, $p < 0.05$**

The result in table 4.10 above revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived mental effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [$f(4,390) = 14.147, p < 0.05$]. Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived social effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State was rejected.

Discussion

The result revealed that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived health effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [$f(4,390) = 10.953, p < 0.05$]. The result of this study is in consonance with findings of Dogan-Sander *et al.* (2021) which reported that prevalence of substance abuse was 55% high of which good proportion of abusers complaint of several health problems such as bronchospasm, whooping and

gastrointestinal illness among others. Cross sectional studies of Verhoog et al. (2020) reported that the health problems are associated with hazardous and harmful drinking of alcohol. White (2020) buttressed that females are more susceptible than males to alcohol-induced liver inflammation, cardiovascular disease, memory blackouts, hangovers, and certain cancers. It is pertinent to note that use of alcohol extensively serve as a modifiable factors to degenerative ailment and disorders.

The result illustrated that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived physical effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [$f(4,390) = 8.798, p < 0.05$]. The result of this study is required because alcohol abusers are likely to be exposed to several physical problems such as injury and violence which is deleterious to this health. The result of this findings is in credence with studies of White et al (2020) whose studies indicated that good percentage of students with reported cases of heavy alcohol consumption are likely to face violence and exposed to physical injury. White (2020) agreed that alcohol abusers are significantly associated with severe cases of alcohol-induced liver inflammation, duodenal ulcer and cancer among others. It is pertinent to note that alcohol intake is one of the major risk factors of degenerative ailments that cause death and other permanent damage to organs.

The result indicated that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived social effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [$f(4,390) = 14.147, p < 0.05$]. The result of this study is expected because the heavy consumption of alcohol affect the coordination of human senses that alter relationship communication with others which has a significant effect on the mental and social health. The result is in agreement with prior studies of Charles et al. (2021) affirmed that heavy consumption of alcohol exposes the users to several medical complications with high proportion of them experiencing psychosocial problems due risky alcohol use. Prior study of Kobiowu (2010) conducted among undergraduates of the Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria which reported that good proportion of victims of substance abuse including alcohol intake are likely to face poor social adjustment which was characterized by situational hostility and low academic grade. Prior studies of Onohwosafe et al (2009) added that Fifty percent (50%) of students with a high academic rating regularly took alcohol, Indian hemp and kola nuts, compared with 54 per cent of low academic performance peers. Becerra and Becerra (2020) reiterated that extension of the alcohol and drugs consumptions problem among adolescents, with special emphasis on the easy access of students to alcoholic beverages at parties, bars, stress and at home contributing to a lot of psychological distress and social problems. It is possible that high intoxication of alcohol on the individual which affect the behaviour, action and harmonious relationship.

The result depicted that there was a significant difference between alcohol intake and perceived mental effect among students of Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State [$f(4,390) = 14.147, p < 0.05$]. Chow et al. (2021) reported that Students with higher levels of depressive symptoms and higher risk of alcohol consumption were more likely to use avoidance for stress-coping. 89.5% of students considered alcohol consumption moderately to very harmful to health, but students demonstrated only moderate knowledge levels of alcohol consumption on health. Jack (2018) examined the influence of excessive intake of alcohol on University of Benin students reported that excessive intake of alcohol can be responsible for student's poor academic performance while some students take alcohol because of home problems. Most students that take alcohol agree to taking it because of their friends are taking it others students agree to taking alcohol when they are depressed believing that alcohol will improve their state of mind and students take alcohol to eliminate fear as the major reasons for alcohol intake.

Conclusion

This study concluded that good proportion of students consuming alcohol was high and it was observed from the findings that heavy alcohol intake exposes the undergraduates of IAUE to several health problems such as physical, social, psychological effects.

Recommendations

In regards to the outcome of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. University management should establish rehabilitative centre in the university to render service to students are already victim of alcohol dependence so as to improve and promote good mental and social health.
2. Students should prioritize their health status by complying with university rule and regulation against drug abuse and negative vices.
3. University management should establish a monitoring team to police the nooks and crannies of the environment where illicit substances are taken.

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